

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

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Executive Summary

The WWRF and WGC

The White Paper on “Multi-RAT Network Architecture” is the outcome of discussions and suggestions in the context of the Wireless World Research Forum (WWRF) meetings and the Working Group C (WGC) in particular, which handles issues related to “Communication Architectures and Technologies”.

Multi-RAT network architecture for the 5G wireless world

Framed in this context, the paper describes the common vision on Multi-RAT network architecture evolution and the introduction of intelligence towards the creation of smart infrastructures beyond the 2020, 5G wireless world. By identifying current trends in mobile networks, the White Paper provides main aspects of key functionalities so as to outline a clear path to future network deployments. NGMN (Next Generation Mobile Networks) has also a dedicated project related to “RAN Evolution” so as to give recommendations on future radio access network architectures.

SRC network and terminal-related functions

In this respect, the Single Radio Controller (SRC) is introduced as one of the concepts for enabling Multi-RAT networks, by discussing the necessity of SRC and detailed conceptual architectures for Multi-RAT base stations (e.g., GSM, UMTS, LTE), and WLAN APs as well. Apart the network side, the White Paper addresses also issues related to User Equipment (UE) which is an integrated part of the network and any change in the network would affect the operation at the UE. As a UE can have detailed local information on channel condition, user experience, and user device status, it is in a unique position in enabling Multi-RAT system. In this respect the White Paper discusses functions at a UE level in support of multi-RAT and SRC.

Intelligent network functionality in the 5G wireless world

Finally, the White Paper concludes with the main trends towards the creation of smart infrastructures by proposing specific enablers for the introduction of intelligence to network elements (including SRC). Introduction of intelligent network functionality and management (e.g., autonomic network management, machine learning etc.) is imperative for performance, energy and cost efficiency of evolved heterogeneous infrastructures, ultra-dense networks, cloud-RANs and M2M/IoT environments.

Way Forward

More White Papers related to innovations in the field of “Communication Architectures and Technologies” will follow in order to address sufficiently several trending topics on: Management of evolved RATs; Ultra-Dense Networks; Dynamic/Flexible Spectrum Management and Spectrum Sharing; Virtualization of Infrastructure by exploiting the concepts of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV); Cloud-RANs.

0. Abbreviations

For the purposes of the present document the following abbreviations apply:

ANDSF	Access network discovery and selection function
AP	Access Point
BSC	Base Station Controller
BSS	Base Station Subsystem
CCE	Control Channel Element
CDMA	Code division multiple access
CN	Core Network
CoMP	Coordinated Multi Point
CSFB	Circuit Switched FallBack
DT	Deutsche Telecom
E2E	End-to-End
eNB	eNode B
FDD	Frequency Division Duplexing
FI	Future Internet
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications
GSMA	GSM Association
HO	Handover
HRPD	High Rate Packet Data
HSPA	High Speed Packet Access
ICIC	Inter-Cell Interference Coordination
IoT	Internet of Things
IWK	Interworking
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KQI	Key Quality Indicator
LTE	Long Term Evolution
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
MAC	Medium Access Control
MBB	Mobile Broadband
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
PCRF	Policy and Charging Rules Function
PDCCH	Physical Downlink Control Channel
PHY	Physical
PRB	Physical Resource Block
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service

RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RBG	Resource Block Group
RCW	RAN Controlled WiFi
RCW	RAN Controlled WiFi AP self-discovery and selection
RNC	Radio Network Controller
Rx	Receiver
SON	Self-organizing network
SRC	Single Radio Controller
TCH	Traffic Channel
TDD	Time Division Duplexing
Tx	Transmitter
UE	User Equipment
UMTS	Universal Mobile Telecommunications System
VoLTE	Voice over LTE
WiFi	Wireless Fidelity
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network

1. Purpose

This document describes our common vision on Multi-RAT Network architecture evolution and the introduction of intelligence towards the creation of smart infrastructures beyond the 2020, 5G wireless world. Its main purpose is to present the current trends in mobile networks and motivate the need for research in specific areas. This document provides main aspects of key functionalities so as to outline a clear path to future networks.

2. Scope

This paper focuses on multi-RAT network architecture evolution. Single Radio Controller (SRC) is introduced as one of the concepts for enabling multi-RAT network. This paper discusses the necessity of SRC and detailed conceptual architectures. The essence is the convergence of multi-RAT controller. SRC can coordinate with multi-RAT base stations (GSM/UMTS/LTE), and WLAN APs.

SRC enriches the connotation of Single-RAN, making its evolution from multi-mode base stations to the integration of multi-mode controller RAN era, possible to achieve a multi-mode terminal, multi-mode base stations, multi-mode controller, and multi-mode wireless E2E Single core network strategy.

This article includes five (5) main parts, as follows:

Chapter 3: Motivation;

Chapter 4: Multi-RAT wireless network architecture evolution;

Chapter 5: Functions of multi-RAT radio access network;

Chapter 6: User devices in multi-RAT;

Chapter 7: Introduction of intelligence to network elements and functions towards the creation of smart infrastructures.

3. Motivation

3.1 Trends and Challenges of MBB

More traffic; Denser networks;
Increased heterogeneity

With mobile broadband (MBB) growth and evolution of the network, the network is becoming dense and complex, each site can be up to seven bands spectrum, five modes (GSM/UMTS/LTE-FDD/TD-LTE/WiFi), and five layers network architecture (Low-frequency macro coverage layer/ high-frequency capacity layer/ hotspot Micro capacity layer/ indoor Pico layer/ WiFi hotspots). If lack of effective coordination, it cannot effectively use all of the wireless network resources and cannot guarantee user experience.

Meanwhile, intelligent terminals, pads and other types of users' equipment (UEs) spread quickly, and the service types of MBB increase rapidly. In such a **multi-layer/multi-band/multi-mode** wireless network, a question on how to improve the utilization efficiency of radio resources, to guarantee QoE of MBB service, to simplify multi-RAT network management, is a huge challenge of the Single-RAN.

3.2 Three targets of multi-RAT network architecture

Enabling unified management and
coordinated usage of resources

At present, the coexistence of several networks assumes the existence of different capabilities. Not all of the existing terminals can support all radio systems, so multi-RAT networks cannot fully substitute for the different type of services to support performance. For example, throughput rate of data is faster than other RATs in the recent LTE network. In addition, the VoLTE (Voice over LTE Initiative) is proposed by GSMA [8] so as to ensure continuity of voice calls when a user moves from an LTE cell to a non-LTE cell. According to service requirements, SRC needs real-time unified management of all wireless resources so as to coordinate the usage of resources in different RATs (Figure 3-1), in order to meet the following targets:

- 1) **Improve the overall utilization of radio resources;**
- 2) **Guarantee users that they get consistent service experience regardless the used system;**
- 3) **Simplify the process of multi-RAT interoperability, reduce network management difficulty;**

Figure 3-1: Three targets of Multi-RAT network architecture

4. Multi-RAT wireless network architecture evolution

4.1 Trend of Multi-RAT Network Evolution

Reducing latency and signaling overheads in a Multi-RAT environment; Minimizing impact on legacy interfaces

Currently 3GPP R12 standard has a number of Multi-RAT IWK WI/SI. One of China Unicom's initiatives focused on RAN3 enhancements for UMTS/HSPA and LTE Interworking (RP-122036[5]), aim to study the UMTS/LTE IWK enhancement. This Study Item will be ended in December 2013. Intel focused on RAN2 WLAN/3GPP Radio Interworking (RP-122038[6]), which aims to enhance operator controlled WLAN IWK, planned to end in December 2013. China Telecom focused on LTE/HRPD Inter-RAT SON in RAN3, which involved self-optimization in LTE and CDMA network. Individual studies on IWK for each pair of RATs, need a global solution for Multi-RAT optimization.

In addition, NGMN launched a project on the evolution of RAN architecture in March 2013 [7]; DT also proposed Multi-RAN architecture with a controller and SKT proposed a Cloud-based architecture with DU pool and Cloud controller for Multi-RAT.

This means that multi-RAT becomes a hot topic among major industrial partners. Multi-RAT operation is a key deployment now and in the coming years. An efficient and general control solution for 2G/3G/LTE/WiFi operations is needed. The control plane optimization regarding Multi-RAT IWK latency and signaling overhead reduction, spectrum utilization and resources management is necessary and important for operators. It should be noted also that the improvement of multi-RAT interoperation should minimize impact on legacy interfaces.

4.2 Single Radio Controller (SRC) for Multi-RAT operation

SRC is a unified controller network entity for unified radio resource and traffic management

SRC is a unified controller network entity that is integrated with RNC/BSC/WiFi AC/eCo functions and provides unified multi-standard radio resource management and unified traffic management. SRC uses common hardware and has software-defined configurable capabilities.

As Figure 4-1 illustrates, in the SRC, eCo and RNC, BSC and other controllers are integrated. Multi-RAT controller and eCo are integrated to a big controller, responsible for the management and coordination of all multi-standard base station radio resources and unified wireless bearer capabilities to Single Core.

Figure 4-1: SRC for multi-RAT selection

5. Functions of multi-RAT radio access network

SRC main functions are related to Joint Radio Resource Management; Joint Mobility Management and Single NAS

NGMN has a dedicated project in its work programme which is related to “RAN Evolution”. According to NGMN, the “RAN Evolution” project evaluates options and gives recommendations for a future radio access network architecture providing optimized operations, higher efficiency and enhanced performance. The aforementioned project proceeds to the evaluation of Centralized Cloud-based RAN, CoMP schemes, Dynamic Spectrum Allocation, Backhaul/Fronthaul, and defines the overarching requirements for a Multi-RAT architecture evolution. This is inline with what is discussed in this White Paper and provides evidence that the proposed SRC functionality and introduction of intelligence is actually needed.

In accordance with managed objects, SRC functionality can be divided into:

- 1) RAT specific controller functions, including:
 - a) BSC/RNC function;
 - b) CoLTE function, which is inter-cell scheduling and power control coordination functions for LTE eNB, including macro and micro coordination and frequency coordination;
 - c) WiFi AC function.
- 2) Coordinator of RAN specific controller for multi-RAT network coordination between cells, including:
 - a) G/U/L inter-RAT coordination for resource scheduling;
 - b) G/U/L/WiFi mobility coordination.

Similar to UMTS/GSM coordination are the management functions within multi-cell in RNC and BSC. SRC as multi-RAT controller is responsible for coordinating G/U/L/WiFi multi-RAT cell. As Figure 5-1 illustrates, SRC functions can be divided into three layers, each of which has multi-RAT coordination function and coordination function among eNBs, as well as the coordination of the cellular network with WiFi.

Figure 5-1: Functions of multi-RAT radio access network

5.1 Flexible RAT Selection

Aiming to reduce the user plane delay within handover process

Each radio access technology is currently E2E coupled (PHY-> MAC/RLC-> NAS/bearer layer, and UE-> RAN-> Core Network-CN). This is not conducive to the efficient use of radio resources. For example, inter-RAT handover (HO) will impact UE/RAN/CN. Thus, this cannot form a real Single RAN converged multi-RAT network.

Service Bearer and NAS layer is separated from specific radio interfaces, allowing the evolution of radio access technology. From the signaling perspective, system interoperability between different RATs is managed by the SRC. For example, inter-RAT handover between G/U/L does not affect the RAN/CN interfaces, reducing the signaling load and delay. From the user plane perspective, the unified bearer layer is conducive to multi-RAT or multi-cell data transmission concurrency. In this respect, UEs may simultaneously send and receive data with TDD and FDD LTE cell, and it also helps to reduce the user plane delay within HO process.

Figure 5-2: Flexible RAT selection

Aiming to reduce signaling overhead and latency

As Figure 5-3 suggests, SRC and core network uses unified interface between SRC and core network. UE and core network use unified NAS. SRC manages multi-RAT radio resources in a unified manner. In inter-RAT HO, SRC directly changes radio interface of RAT but NAS remains, so CN is not involved in HO procedure; thus signaling latency is reduced. Radio interface technology is decoupled from CN.

Figure 5-3: SRC and Core unified interfaces

5.1.1 Multi-RAT call redirection for signaling and latency reduction

5.1.1.1 Application Example 1: CSFB based on SRC

Figure 5-4: Application example 1

The following procedure is envisaged:

- 1: UE sends Voice service request (G/U NAS signaling) to SRC via eNB,
- 2: SRC further forwards the request to MSC
- 3: MSC and UE exchange G/U NAS signaling (carried over LTE) to complete service request procedure
- 4: MSC indicates SRC to establish Radio Bearer for the UE,
- 5: SRC establishes RB via BTS/NodeB (not eNB) for the UE;
- 6: SRC indicates UE about BTS/NodeB radio resource assignment information
- 7: UE establishes radio link to BTS/NB according to indicated resource information,
- 8: UE starts to use voice service

5.1.1.1 Application Example 2 : Multi-RAT fast handover

Optimized Multi-RAT handover and reduced signaling overhead

In Single RAN scenario, G/U/L cell is in a base station. RNC/BSC and the eNB mobility function are in one controller which is located within the SRC entity. To this respect, some inter-RAT handover signaling between network elements is internal signaling within SRC. In Single Core scenario, UE session context of G/U/L different RAT is implemented as a single database record. Multi-RAT handover is actually a session context update. Multi-RAT handover can be optimized to the similar process with intra-frequency LTE handover process, i.e., the UE has established a link to the target cell and released the source cell link, then notified the core network to update user data routing of UE from the source cell to the target cell.

As Figure 5-5 illustrates, during the L->U handover process, SRC completes radio link handover internally, and then notifies the UE to update context of the core network. The signaling from Single RAN to Single Core reduced from 11 to 5. A number of RNC->eNB signaling can be simplified internal signaling within SRC entity which can reduce the signaling delay and enhance the handover success rate.

Figure 5-5: Application example 2

5.2 Multi-RAT Joint Radio Operation

SRC-based inter-RAT joint resource scheduling scheme can achieve higher spectral efficiency and interference coordination

With the decrease of GSM traffic, operators generally consider refarming of GSM spectrum. On the other hand, LTE also needs "gold spectrum" to achieve full coverage. The utilization of limited spectrum bands to G/L RAT has become an urgent problem. Vodafone, China Mobile and other operators want to be able to ensure LTE network coverage and service availability.

Figure 5-6: Multi-RAT joint radio operation [7]

Usually spectrum refarming is statically allocated spectrum resources to different RATs. The problem is that spectrum utilization is low. Spectrum sharing between different RATs is more flexible, but it faces the problem of interference. SRC-based inter-RAT joint resource scheduling scheme can achieve higher spectral efficiency and interference coordination.

Figure 5-7: Spectrum sharing

Spectrum of GSM traffic channel is shared with both ends of LTE carrier

Inter-RAT JS solution can solve shared spectrum on the scheduling level. Its basic principle is that spectrum of GSM TCH is shared with both ends of LTE carrier. Since the center of LTE carrier is not shared with GSM system, the UE can read the synchronization channel and broadcast channel of LTE without interfering with GSM. However, the downlink PDCCH is scattered throughout downlink band and it is expected that interference of PDCCH would be significant. The solution to this problem is to reduce the coding order of PDCCH and use CCE.

Figure 5-8: Inter-RAT JS concept

Inter-RAT JS solution process is described below:

- 1) SRC Configures LTE secondary carrier and GSM TCH are running on the same band, covering the same area;
- 2) GSM system takes the shared spectrum as dedicated spectrum as usual, so GSM does not sense that spectrum is dynamically shared with LTE;
- 3) LTE system uses PRB of secondary carrier when GSM does not use in spectrum and time domain. In time domain, since GSM system has fixed scheduling schema (1 timeslot per user), LTE cell can avoid interference by using timeslot that GSM does not assign the TCH to user. In frequency domain, GSM and LTE can avoid interference by staggering their respective scheduling of TCH and PRB.

Figure 5-9: Resource block utilization

5.3 LTE joint radio resource management

Maximizing the network utilization and optimizing the network performance

LTE eCo function handles interference coordination between eNB. Currently, 3GPP defined ICIC, CoMP function needs to realize mesh link between eNB (that is any of two eNB in a cluster needs to have links). Interaction efficiency is low (scale of N^2). LTE eCo entity obtains information from all eNBs and then configures unified configuration to avoid interference. Interaction efficiency is high (N^2).

In the interference limited scenario, different nodes need differentiated power optimization. Different scheduling users have different optimal power point, so the optimal power adjustment strategy should consider optimizing power together with scheduling, this is called CSPC.

CSPC algorithm uses virtual scheduling within cluster and uses the historical value estimation method out of clusters. It adaptively selects optimal transmit power according to the user, load and interference information. CSPC combines scheduling and power control to select the optimal power level and perform joint virtual scheduling based on each candidate power level, then judge the pros and cons of the power level based on scheduling result. The rule judgments adopt utility function and combine with the existing product. It uses PF scheduling priority formula. Therefore, the goal of every power optimization can maximize the whole network utilization and optimize the whole network performance.

Figure 5-10: LTE joint radio resource management

Cluster is mutually non-overlapping set of cells. Cells within a cluster are tightly coupled and fast information exchange. Cells between clusters are loosely coupled and have slow information exchange. CSPC divides the whole network into some non-overlapping clusters. CSPC between clusters performs optimization independently. CSPC in cluster performs loop self-optimization in accordance with sequential serial from macro to micro cell. Meanwhile, CSPC will divide entire bandwidth into several RBGs, each RB within one RBG use the same power level. CSPC can be done independently for different RBG.

SRC is responsible for collection information for CSPC, algorithm decision and indicates the eNB scheduling which relies on backhaul delay. There is some performance loss in the non-ideal backhaul scenarios (80ms delay leads to performance loss of 10%).

5.4 Joint Mobility Management

Optimizing joint mobility and reducing handover latency

Multi-RAT joint mobility optimization, main points are:

- a) To optimize mobility KPI and reduce handover delay using G/U/L multi-standard base station, multi-standard controller, and even the Single Core network. These include inter-RAT handover optimization, inter-RAT multi-cell joint camping, accessing, and congestion management.
- b) To include connection state load balancing (MLB) based on multi-RAT handover, as well as idle state load balancing based on multi-RAT joint camping.

5.4.1 Inter-RAT joint mobility management including Mobility load balancing

Network performance depends on the optimization of antenna parameters and network configuration parameters

In general, multi-RAT load balancing in SRC does a unified resource management based on service distribution and capability of network equipment, assigns UE to the resident cell, and monitors the KPI of entire network and users QoE. It includes strategies of a unified camping, strategy of unified admission control and congestion control, as well as strategies of mobility load balancing.

In the current network, the standards of KPI and QoE for operators and end users are different. It is necessary to adaptively learn evaluation strategy of operators and end-users, so as to establish subjective evaluation mappings of KPI and KQI with operators and end users.

Figure 5-11: Inter-RAT joint mobility management including mobility load balancing

Also, as Figure 5-11 depicts, service distribution and hardware capabilities of network equipment is objective, so the network KPI and service KQI actually depends on the optimization of antenna parameters and network configuration parameters.

Optimization algorithm of antenna parameter is relatively mature, such as Powell algorithm, genetic algorithms, etc. New RFSO algorithm real-time updates service distribution according to MDT information and

quickly adjust the antenna parameters, to make the areas where the service volume or delay-sensitive services is relatively concentrated to have better signal quality. The basic principle is to refine traffic distribution to the geographic grid, and to do the appropriate aggregation from traffic hotspots, and then polymerize traffic hotspot to the station according to the traffic distribution with the principle of mutual exclusion between stations and cohesion inside station. Finally, cells of site are divided. Simulations show that new RFSO algorithm is 20 times faster than traditional optimization algorithm; it is suitable for deployment on the SRC.

Configuration strategy of network parameters is related to implementation. Generally it needs to consider the QoS requirements and network capabilities, load levels, as well as optimal adaptation subjective feelings of end users and operators. For example, users may preferentially reside at the highest standard cells, but if it initiates a voice call it is best to ensure it resides on best coverage circuit domain network. Another example is small packet service. It may select UMTS or LTE cell according to the package size, frequency, cell load and other factors. Many of these strategies applicable conditions are correlated to each other and are not suitable for human administration. So it needs to use intelligent algorithms to build configuration and KPI/KQI relationship and adaptively allocate resources for the UE, to ensure the QoE of UE is best and irrelevant with the RAT and hierarchy of cell.

5.5 Cellular and WiFi IWK

WiFi offloading and interworking of 3GPP and non-3GPP systems set new challenges to operators

Because WiFi uses unlicensed spectrum, more operators started using WiFi hotspots to offload the load of cellular network. 3GPP began discussing how the two fields in SA coexist from R6. But during R12, 3GPP began to discuss how the two coexist in RAN side.

Specific needs of cellular networks hosted on SRC and WiFi collocated, include:

- a) Self-discovery and selection of WiFi AP. That is how UEs detect WiFi AP timely, and how UEs access APs.
- b) UEs access WiFi AP and traffic diversion. That is how it assigns IP address for UEs accessed (access security is out of the scope of this article). How to keep the service continuity of UE between cellular network and WiFi during traffic diversion.

RCW solution requires that the cellular network protocol stack of UE can control the WiFi AP function of UE. 3GPP R8 defined that the operator sends to UE by the user plane ANDSF (Device Management protocol defined by OMA). Then UE decides whether to access WiFi AP based on the measurement results and the operator's policy. However, due to the static policy, it does not indicate load information of cellular network and WiFi AP, and it does not indicate whether the location of the UE has WiFi AP or not. So application of ANDSF solution is limited. Figure 5-12 shows the differences of RCW and ANDSF.

Figure 5-12: Cellular and Wi-Fi IWK

5.5.1 WiFi AP Self-discovery and selection based SRC

SRC controls the cellular network and the WiFi AP within cellular network coverage area

The RAN Controlled WiFi AP self-discovery and selection solution (abbreviated as RCW) is that a UE finds WiFi APs and selects/accesses WiFi AP through the RAN signaling interactions with the UE. In this solution, SRC controls the cellular network and the WiFi AP within cellular network coverage area, and judges if the UE is under the cover of the WiFi AP based on the cellular network and/or WiFi AP signal strength reported by UE. Similarly, when the UE leaves the WiFi AP, SRC can control UE and access cellular networks for communication based on signal strength.

In RCW solution, SRC determines which UE access is based on the cellular network and WiFi load levels. SRC can determine the UE migration also based on UE bearer's QCI, and the user level (originally used in scheduling) and other information. Optionally, SRC gets more policy information by interacting with 3GPP ANDSF or PCRF. In this respect, the operator can configure the ANDSF / PCRF, and determines part or all of the UEs which do the session migration according to the service type of UE, or determines the migration of the UE according to the user's service subscription etc. (Figure 5-13).

Figure 5-13: WiFi AP self-discovery and selection

6. User devices in multi-RAT

Deployment of SRC concept at network side would require a corresponding change at the UE side

User equipment is an integrated part of the network, any change in the network would affect the operation at the UE. As a UE have detailed local information on channel condition, user experience, and user device status, it is in a unique position in enabling multi-RAT system. In this section, we discuss functions at the UEs in support of multi-RAT and SRC.

6.1 Multi-radio controller at the UE

Deployment of SRC concept at network side would require a corresponding change at the UE side. The function of multi-radio controller can be two folds:

- Cooperate with the SRC at network side for joint resource scheduling and mobility control
- Ensure compatibility between network SRC commands and UE pre-defined radio access policies

Multi-radio controller at the UE side can be a counterpart of the SRC at the network side. It would work together with the SRC at the network side in scheduling the UE's multi-radio access and transmission/reception. This function is especially needed when the control of SRC over UE is loose, i.e., the SRC scheduling UE's multi-radio operation in a static or semi-static way. The multi-radio controller at the UE should be able to dynamically schedule UE's communication over different RATs based on the channel/traffic conditions and the UE's QoS requirement as well as the commands from the SRC in the network.

Moreover, as a UE would have pre-defined policies in control of the radio access function and priority, compatibility between SRC commands and UE pre-defined radio access policies needs to be ensured. The multi-radio controller would be a coordinator to determine UE's behavior by jointly considering SRC commands and UE policies.

Figure 6-1 illustrates functions of the multi-RAT controller in the UE. The interaction between the network SRC and the UE multi-RAT controller can be either SRC push instruction/commands to the multi-RAT controller or the multi-RAT controller request information from the SRC.

Figure 6-1 Functions of the UE multi-RAT controller

6.2 Measurement and reporting

UE measurements and reporting would be key references for efficient multi-RAT operation. Some of the measurements the UE need to report to the network are as follows:

- Channel condition across different RATs

- Real-time traffic conditions
- Perceived quality of service from the serving RATs
- Battery usage status

The channel condition is needed in cross-RAT radio scheduling, RAT selection and mobility control. The real-time traffic condition provides timely information on the active UE applications and the pending data transmission. With real-time traffic information, the network would better predict the upcoming traffic load and schedule resource allocation accordingly. The UE perceived quality of service provides information on traffic load and the service quality of the serving RATs. Such information can be used to facilitate operations like network traffic steering and load balancing mobile association. The battery usage status of a UE needs to be counted in RAT and service selection. For example, when the UE is in the low battery state, the RAT with the lowest power consumption would be selected and the serving data rate would be adjusted for power conservation.

Figure 6-2 UE reporting procedure

Figure 6-2 shows how the UE measurement and reporting could reach out to the SRC and subsequently affect network operation. The UE reporting messages can be first collected and processed by its serving RAT BS. The serving BS would then report the synthetic message (by considering both UE reporting and its own measurement) to the SRC. With the received synthetic messages from different sources, the SRC can then generate proper commands to guide RAN operation.

6.3 Mobility support

UE supports mobility management in two ways:

- Provide measurement report to the network to facilitate mobility management
- Directly conduct mobility control

Mobility in 3GPP RATs are normally controlled by network. However, in non-3GPP RATs, such as WLAN, mobility is usually UE-controlled. With the network evolves towards multi-RATs convergence, a unified solution is needed on the mobility management across both 3GPP and non-3GPP RATs. The network controlled mobility would be a preferable solution in terms of performance and resource usage. The evolution towards unified network controlled mobility would be a step-by-step effort. At the intermediated stages, we would expect a UE controlled solution for non-3GPP RATs with tighter coupling with the network.

7. Introduction of intelligence to network elements and functions towards the creation of smart infrastructures

Increased performance, energy and cost efficiency to 5G wireless networks through the introduction of intelligence to network functionality

The aforementioned sections raised issues related to multi-RAT network architecture evolution and SRC functions on the network and UE side. This section deals with concepts related to introduction of intelligence to network elements and functions (including SRC) so as to increase performance, energy and cost efficiency to 5G wireless networks. Specifically, it is widely believed that the emerging wireless world will be characterized by increased data and signaling traffic, various levels of mobility (high, moderate mobility, static users) as well as diverse interference conditions. Heterogeneity will also be a dominant feature which combines, ultra-dense networks, mixed usage of cells of diverse sizes and access points with different characteristics in an operating network. Wireless networks pose specific requirements which need to be fulfilled. To that respect, approaches for introducing intelligence and cognition in the wireless Future Internet (FI) are investigated by the research community. Intelligence shall provide cost-efficient solutions at which a certain application/ service/ quality provision is achieved. All these features shall lead to the exploitation of a cognitive management ecosystem for further advancements on cognitive network management for future wireless infrastructures.

7.1 Intelligent management of heterogeneous infrastructures and Ultra-Dense Networks

Optimized networks with increased capacity, ultra-low latency, very low downtime and losses

Introduction of intelligence is vital in heterogeneous infrastructures since it enables optimal handling of complex contextual situations (i.e., traffic fluctuations, various mobility levels, interference). To that respect, distributed solutions for adaptive/ predictive network topology and resource allocation configurations will lead to:

- Selection of cells to operate from large sets: Transceivers that will be involved in the handling of a situation (flexible cell layouts);
- Handling of many spectrum bands: Selection of band, width that will be assigned to be operated by the transceivers (spectrum management);
- Cells of different technologies: Handling the multi-technology aspect;
- Traffic distribution to cells: Various time scales and degrees of distribution;
- Global optimality with respect to QoE; energy efficiency; overall cost efficiency, etc.

Figure 7-1 depicts the introduction of intelligence to heterogeneous infrastructures by enabling selection of cells and technology (RAT) to use, selection of spectrum and traffic distribution.

Figure 7-1: Introducing intelligence to heterogeneous infrastructures

7.2 Intelligent management of Cloud-RANs

Another promising area which can benefit from the introduction intelligence is the migration of functionalities to the cloud by forming the so called Cloud-RAN. Intelligence will enable the:

- Placement of very light transmission units – intelligence in the “core”
- Software components (system functionality) in repositories
- Dynamic software activation and deployment to various servers
 - Smart management of available resources, e.g., given the context of operation find the physical elements that should be used, the allocation of functional elements to physical elements and the physical elements inter-connections
- Heuristic, knowledge based solutions

Figure 7-2 provides a visual representation of the Cloud-RAN notion by assuming the migration of functional from base stations (macro, small cells) to cloud constructs.

Figure 7-2: Introducing intelligence to Cloud-RANs

7.3 Intelligent management of M2M/IoT environments

A vast amount of objects in our ambience towards the Internet of Things (IoT) leads to the realization of diverse networking constructs encompassing various kinds of smart devices. Intelligence will provide essential functionality for the efficient creation, deployment and management of objects/networks, reduced OPEX, QoE (time for service delivery, maintenance), energy consumption as well as service provision dynamically tailored to the needs of end users. Figure 7-3 shows the impact of intelligence to the IoT domain by adding a cognition layer which will be responsible of proceeding to self-management, context-awareness and learning functionalities.

Figure 7-3: Introducing intelligence to M2M/IoT environments

8. Summary

This White Paper provides an insight on technological achievements, trends and challenges of multi-RAT network architectures. The introduction and the necessity of the SRC in the Single RAN/ HetNet era are elaborated. In addition, the potential coordination of SRC with multi-RAT base stations (i.e., GSM/UMTS/LTE), and WLAN APs is investigated in both the network and UE sides. Also, the description of a multi-RAT wireless network architecture evolution as well as the functions of multi-RAT radio access network are enriched by elaborating on the notion of intelligence towards the creation of smart infrastructures which will be vital for the beyond 2020 and 5G wireless world.

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